

THE IMPORTANCE OF PHYSICAL RESPONSE METHOD IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

Nasiba Mirzayeva Bakhtiyar kizi

English teacher at Tashkent State University of Uzbek language
and literature named after Alisher Navoi

E-mail: nasiba.mirzaeva.98@bk.ru

Phone: +998900920027

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Annotation. The article describes the elements of the method of physical reaction and their practical application in foreign language classes with primary school students. The essence of this method is revealed, historical information and examples of its practical application are given, the pros and cons of using this method in foreign language lessons are revealed.

Keywords: foreign language, method of physical reaction, primary school students, motivation.

Аннотация. В статье описываются элементы метода физической реакции и их практическое применение на занятиях по иностранному языку с учащимися начальной школы. Раскрывается суть данного метода, приводятся исторические сведения и примеры его практического применения, раскрываются плюсы и минусы использования данного метода на уроках иностранного языка.

Ключевые слова: иностранный язык, способ физического реагирования, учащиеся младших классов, мотивация.

Introduction. In the age of information technology and international communication, foreign language proficiency the language is necessary for a highly qualified specialist. In this connection, the problem of effective teaching of a foreign language is relevant, starting from primary school age.

In the pedagogical and psychological literature, the problem of using various methods as a means of increasing motivation among schoolchildren in English lessons has been well studied. Among modern researchers, the following are currently studying this problem: T.O. Gordeeva [7], V.V. Gizhitsky,

M.V. Arkhipova [2], N.V. Shutova [5], O.V. Smolovik [4] and many others. Moreover, some researchers claim that the problem of children's motor development is particularly relevant in modern Russian society, where there is a significant deterioration in the health and physical development of the younger generation [1]. In this regard, it seems important to us to single out one of the most effective methods of teaching a foreign language to younger schoolchildren, which increases the motivation of children, promotes the activation of mental processes, and corresponds to the age-related psychological and pedagogical characteristics of primary school children. This method is the method of physical response.

Presentation of the main material of the article. The method of physical response (Total physical response) was created by the American psychologist James Asher. TPR gained its popularity in the 70s of the 20th century. This method is based on the theory of two hemispheres of the brain, where the left hemisphere is responsible for logic and

consciousness, and the right hemisphere is responsible for intuition and subconsciousness. Traditional methods of learning a foreign language assume its assimilation using the functions of the left hemisphere (e.g. mechanical memorization, repetition). When learning a foreign language using the method of physical response, the activation of the right hemisphere occurs and the process of mastering a foreign language occurs more efficiently. The essence of the methodology has been repeatedly stated by the followers of J. Asher, but we decided

to appeal to one of his articles, which is called "Language on command: a method of complete physical response when teaching a language." This article includes two parts. In the first, J. Asher reveals the essence of this technique, in the second he justifies it, explaining the functioning of the hemispheres of the brain human. According to the author, mastering a foreign language is most difficult for schoolchildren. According to the results of the study, success in learning a foreign language was revealed only in 5% of schoolchildren.

The difference between these results and the indicators of six-year-old children learning their native language without schooling is enormous [8]. An interesting question is about the differences in the process of mastering the native language in childhood and a foreign language at a later age. But the author does not disclose it. James Asher does not report on the physiological difference in the development of the brain of primary school children and children, as well as on various processes on which are based on the acquisition of native and foreign languages. Scientists take into account the well-known fact that the acquisition of the native language occurs together with the formation of the brain, and the study of a foreign language occurs later, when the brain is already formed, respectively, the principles by which the development of the native language takes place cannot be equally effective in mastering a foreign language.

Moreover, neurophysiologists note the threshold age when "natural" language acquisition becomes impossible. It is determined that if a child under three or four years old does not master the language (for various reasons, either physiological (diseases of the auditory pathways and vision), or social (a child from a dysfunctional family, parents ignore the child), in the future speech development becomes impossible, since the brain structures are formed, and the child does not perceive language physiologically.

The most active phase of language acquisition (the "launch" of learning processes) occurs when the child is 9-12 months old. Nevertheless, the professor-psychologist mentions that a student needs a large amount of academic hours when mastering a foreign language in order to follow the path of a child. "However taking into account the fact that children are effectively learning the language, and schoolchildren and adults are experiencing great problems, it can be assumed that their way of mastering the language is effective" [8]. It is fully recognized that it will be useful for any teacher to know the way in which a child learns his native language for effective teaching of a foreign language. Linguists and psychologists all over the world have advanced in the study of psychology, and speech of children. And James Asher is based on the principles of language formation in children. Let 's highlight three main points of the way of children 's speech development:

"1). Listening skills precede speaking." 2). Many statements addressed to children contain an incentive to action, more than 50% are formulated in the form of commands. "3) Listening to speech leads to a "willingness" to speak [6]. Using this method, the presentation of the language occurs through the imperative mood, students react with the help of an action

response. Researchers note that today it is necessary to competently build social contacts of a child with teachers and with peers who significantly influence the mental development and social formation of each child [3], which can also be facilitated by the use of the method of physical response. When implementing this method the teacher is presented in the role of a director directing actors, i.e. students, as a parent regulating the activities of children in various domestic situations. When working with elementary-level children, the teacher develops the learning process from elementary commands. For example, a teacher says a command statement in a foreign language and shows an action-movement to students. Over time, the commands become more complicated. During further training, past and future tenses and other elements are introduced language. In the method of physical reaction there is no translation and rules, the presence of which we observe it in traditional methods. Translation is not necessary, because the word is included in the network connecting this lexical unit with others. As time passes, students begin to "feel the language" and incorrect statements will be unnatural for them.

There are many types of TPR training: visual visualizations, guessing, performing physical actions, working with pictures (cards), telling stories accompanied by actions, etc.

According to proponents, the effectiveness of this method is determined by the following factors: progress as children due to 1) listening to the language, 2) being in a safe environment, 3) not forced, but free desire to speak. This method is especially effective in teaching younger students, taking into account their age and psychological characteristics.

To implement the elements of the physical response method, various types and types of tasks are used, here are some of them. First of all, it is worth noting that it is preferable to conduct classes in groups. From the first lessons, the teacher focuses on verbs, introduces them through the imperative mood, then connects nouns (mostly objects surrounding the guys). The training of new lexical units takes place in the following stages: 1) The teacher says the command and repeatedly performs the action together with the students. 2) Then the teacher calls the command, and the students perform the action independently. 3) The teacher addresses each student individually, offering to execute a certain command. Entering each subsequent command, the teacher relies on the above steps. There may be a sufficient number of them during one lesson, but individual ones should not be neglected age-related mental characteristics of schoolchildren, because younger schoolchildren are able to learn from 7 to 10 new words per lesson. At the end of the lesson, there is a complete repetition of everything studied. After all the subjects in the class are mastered, the use of pictures, abstract concepts begins (also through role-playing games), then whole stories are studied, linking vocabulary with times. Only after about 20 hours

of classes, students begin to pronounce words aloud, give commands to each other. After a while, they begin to read texts, then learn to write [6]. Here are other examples of the implementation of this method: Simon Says is a classic exercise in this technique, which is widely used to study body parts. But this exercise can be carried out, for example, to teach children the direction.

It is necessary to prepare a place so that children can move around safely, put flashcards on desks (house, market, school, etc.), or hang a map on a board, that is, arrange a "district", and students give each other directions where to go: "Simon says go straight, Simon says turn left." Charades is another classic game.

It is best suited for teaching action verbs, The Present Continuous Tense tense, lexical units on the topic "Sport" and some other topics. For example, first we show a flashcard, then we depict this action independently, naming the verb and requiring choral repetition from children. Then, we form two teams. Each student must take a flashcard, picture or map with sports written on it and show the movement so that his or her teammates can guess what it is. The guys from the team respond with complete sentences: He is playing football. In this exercise, the following is done the emphasis is not only on the assimilation of new vocabulary, but also on grammatical structures. Songs. Undoubtedly, children like to sing. Taking this fact into account, the teacher can add movements and facial expressions that are integrated with the lyrics. This element of the method can be used in teaching both vocabulary and grammar. Walk around the classroom. This activity is great for kids and adults. You will need several objects or props to use. We show the actions and name them. Then we call actions and ask students to show them. Examples: - You open the door. - You come to the blackboard. - You take a chalk. -You close the window. -You take your pencil. -You look at him. Role-playing games- pantomimes. This game is also liked by adult students, but it is especially useful for children. Give each student a role, but he must fulfill it without words. For example, the first student needs to go to the polyclinic, and he asks how to get through. But he's lost his voice, and he can't say a word. His second disciple, he stops on the street and asks to show the way, but this person cannot speak, the second one must understand his gestures to find out where he needs to go. Hands up! – Hands up! An active game of mindfulness. The task of the presenter is to confuse the children by calling one command, while performing another.

For example, the presenter says "Clap hands!" ("clap your hands"), and he stomps at the same time. Students should be very careful when executing the commands that the presenter calls. If the child makes a mistake, he is eliminated from the game. The most attentive student becomes the leader. Transformations. Students become in circle and, touching each other with a "magic wand", transform each other and transform themselves.

Sample replicas of children: I am a princess and you are a mouse. I am not a mouse, I am a kitten and you are a monster. I am not a monster. I am a pilot and you are a sandwich. In this case, the use of the verb "To be" in affirmative and negative sentences is worked out, as well as new lexical units, or previously studied vocabulary is updated. Carousel. The teacher arranges the chairs around in this way, so that there are one fewer chairs than there are children in the classroom. The teacher explains a certain sound, for example [w]. The students start walking around the chairs while the teacher slowly pronounces any words in English. As soon as he calls the word with the sound [w], the children should take a seat on the chairs.

If the child does not have time to take a place, he is eliminated from the game. This exercise is designed to form the phonetic perception of foreign language speech. Despite the fact that the method of physical response is not specializes in phonetics, however, some of its elements can be used for this purpose. The tasks proposed above are available (feasible) and interesting. The child is not afraid that he will be given a bad mark, therefore, he is liberated, active and motivated to learn a foreign language.

It is impossible to omit the fact that each method has a number of advantages and disadvantages, including the method of physical response, which we need to take into account when choosing the elements of the method in teaching younger students. I must say that the method of physical reaction has proven itself well self-employed and widely used abroad. Undoubtedly, this method is interesting, unusual and very effective in the early stages of

learning a foreign language. But, nevertheless, it has its drawbacks, and we must highlight them. Among the advantages, it was determined that the method of physical reaction is well suited for teaching language in the classroom, at a time when vocabulary related to actions is being studied.

It can be used to teach the imperative mood, as well as for various tenses and aspects. The method of physical response can be a useful alternative to teaching children with dyslexia who have difficulty learning a foreign language through traditional methods. According to the proponents of the method of physical reaction, in addition to the above, it has a number of advantages: -Students are always on the move, and this reflects the main age characteristics of primary school children and contributes to their physical development; -Simple actions of the elements of the method do not require much preparation on the part of the teacher; -The method of physical response is optimal for kinesthetic students who need to be active in the classroom; -

The presented method is effective for children and adults; -It is easier to learn words through commands, and they are remembered with less effort; -The lesson itself is interesting and helps to increase motivation; -Elements of the methodology are excellent ways to activate students. Among the disadvantages: this method does not provide a tool for independent development. Learning the language traditionally, we learn to impose language on a grid of rules, and then we can figure out the grammar ourselves using theory and exercises and memorize new material well enough. There are people who are logicians, for whom it is traditionally much easier to learn a language. And the method of physical reaction, unfortunately, will not save you from mistakes, although no other method can guarantee this. Many scientists believe that without knowing the rules and not being in an English-speaking environment all the time, a person cannot get the same "sense of language".

And it is almost impossible to find out how to say correctly where and what needs to be agreed in a sentence without using any theoretical sources.

Conclusions. Thus, it can be concluded that the method of teaching a foreign language to younger schoolchildren disclosed in this article is an effective element of teaching that complements traditional foreign language assignments. This method increases the motivation of students, activates their mental activity, promotes the motor development of children, fully meets the age and psychological and pedagogical characteristics of primary school students. There is a significant variety of elements of the method that can be widely applied in the study of certain topics.

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